

D7.1.

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

D7.1

WP7, T 7.1

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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- *PU = Public
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CHANGE HISTORY / REVIEW TABLE

v/d	Date	Beneficiary and Description	Author
D1	01/04/2025	ICONS shared first draft with PNO to align CD plan with Exploitation	Chiara Serio
D2	11/04/2025	PNO reviewed plan and validated stakeholder groups	Edgar Valverde
D3	28/04/2025	ICONS provided feedback and completed internal quality check to share final draft with internal reviewers	Jasmin Jabbarpour
D4	06/05/2025	BFL, CITTA DI TORINO completed the internal review and provided input	Eva Sonck, Mariangela Pastorello
D5	19/05/2025	ICONS incorporated reviewers' input and finalized draft for technical review of CSCP	Sofia Francescutto, Jasmin Jabbarpour
D6	21/05/2025	CSCP completed technical review and provided input	Arlind Xhelili
V1	29/05/2025	ICONS integrated CSCP input	Sofia Francescutto, Jasmin Jabbarpour
V1.5	08/01/2026	ICONS integrated minor feedback received from the PO after first submission	Sofia Francescutto, Jasmin Jabbarpour

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ACRONYMS

C&D/CD – Communication and Dissemination
C&D&E – Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation
WP – Work Package
CS – Citizen Science
BPB – Best Practice Book
KER – Key Exploitable Results
KPI – Key Performance Indicator
CEI – Community Engagement Index
PEI – Publication Engagement Index
SEI – Social Engagement Index
WEI – Website Engagement Index

1 INTRODUCTION

SPOON project wants to use citizen science to lead a transformative change towards a fair and sustainable food system for all layers of society. Citizens and communities will have a primary role in classifying, collecting and analysing data in order to reduce food insecurity and enable a more sustainable food consumption behaviour.

It is therefore pivotal to develop and manage an effective communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy. The plan herein presented provides an overview of the communication and dissemination activities as part of the Work Package 7 aiming to:

Figure 1. C&D&E

- **Raise visibility and understanding** of the project and inform target groups and broader communities on the benefits and impacts of the project (**C**).
- **Share knowledge** and engage key players increasing the acceptance of innovative approaches such as the data-driven approach to policy recommendations (**D**).
- Aligning with the exploitation pathways to ensure the uptake and upscale of the **project's results**, in this specific case through the SPOON Academy (**E**).

This plan is supported by a preliminary mapping of stakeholders, the analysis of

their needs and the definition of their role and level of involvement with project's results. In D7.2, after the drafting of the first exploitation plan, the CD plan will be adjusted as needed.

Dissemination and communication actions start from the very beginning of the project, by identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders (e.g., citizens, food system actors, scientific community, decisionmakers, policymakers, consumer associations, NGOs). During the project, these stakeholders will have access to projects outputs and tools such as the website, the SPOON toolset etc. and integrate them as part of their strategy. Moreover, networking will be crucial to exploiting synergies with projects, initiatives, and partnerships whose purpose is to change the food system.

The impact and effectiveness of the strategy will be continuously monitored and measured through a proprietary methodology developed by ICONS based on a set of indicators and indexes, among them the Community Engagement – Index (CEI). Monitoring activities will provide continuous feeds to the C&D plan to optimize and upgrade it along the different project phases.

2 C&D STRATEGY

2.1 APPROACH AND OBJECTIVES

The C&D plan is essential to boost awareness about SPOON's impact in reducing food insecurity, while stimulating interest and engagement on the active role citizens will and should take to lead the transformation across the food value chain in consumption behaviour.

The SPOON approach aims to:

- Develop an analytical framework and increase understanding of factors influencing healthy and sustainable food consumption;
 - Implement Citizen Science Labs (CSLs) and Behaviour Change Interventions (BCI) with citizens and food stakeholders to collect, visualise and interpret data on consumers' consumption behaviours and their local food purchasing and consumption environments;
 - Create and deploy the SPOON digital toolset that includes a multimedia questionnaire generator and a personal data wallet to enable data collection and analysis (citizen science);
 - Establish a GDPR-compliant data governance framework focusing on privacy, data sharing, and interoperability;
 - Produce guidelines and a capacity-building programme for citizen science and consumer behaviour change projects aiming to exploit, replicate and accelerate project learnings, insights and results
- Draft policy recommendations to enhance data-driven policies through better use of citizen data, digital tools, and cross-sector collaboration.

The table below presents the analysis of the needs addressed by SPOON and its expected outcomes:

Table 1. Needs and results

Specific needs	Expected results
Incomplete understanding of barriers and motivations and drivers of citizens' food consumption behaviour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-developed innovative CS projects, covering and involving different target groups, including vulnerable • Capacity building programme based on developed guidelines for CS.
Insufficient research on the effects of CS on behaviour change in food consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database of best CS practices in food system transformation. • Co-design behaviour change interventions with actors from food value chain.

<p>Low trust of citizens in how their personal data is being collected and used</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPOON toolset. • Recommendations for common data governance framework. • SWOT analysis of existing digital tools for sharing personal food data.
<p>Dispersion of personal data across sectors hinders holistic decision-making</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy recommendations. • Open access datasets of personal food data.
<p>Need for innovative and co-design approaches to promote sustainable and fair food consumption.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results and insights from CSLs as basis for discussion and recommendations.

2.2 RELATIONS WITH OTHER ACTIVITIES

The Communication and Dissemination activities are particularly effective when a strong linkage is established with the other WPs. The visual map below (Figure 2) showcases how all WPs can and should feed WP7. C&D aims to take technical content from other WPs, transform it and communicate it to a wider public and disseminate to specific targets.

Figure 2. How all WPs feed WP7

In particular, WP3 and WP4 have an important role in setting the framework and then guiding the implementation of the CSLs. It will be important to ensure a good communication flow to be informed on the updates of CSLs at local level, contribute to keep CSLs participants engaged and raise awareness about the methodologies used in SPOON, such as citizen science and behavioural change interventions. The important relation with WP6 is explained in the following subchapter.

2.3 RELATION WITH EXPLOITATION

SPOON's exploitation strategy developed under WP6 is tightly connected to the projects C&D strategy outlined in this deliverable D7.1. While C&D activities aim to ensure visibility, engagement and awareness of SPOON's mission and outcomes, the exploitation strategy seeks to translate those outcomes into long-term impact, uptake, and replication. This mutual reinforcement is central to SPOON's impact pathway.

C&D plays a key enabling role for exploitation by creating visibility for SPOON's Key Exploitable Results (KERs). KERs will be continuously monitored throughout project duration; during the elaboration of the first C&D plan, the current list of outlined KERs is presented in the following table:

Table 2. KERs name and main owners

KER ID	NAME	MAIN KER OWNER
1	Expanded framework on food environment, including behavioural factors affecting European sustainable and healthy food consumption	EV-ILVO
2	Online database of best practices using CS in food system transformation	EV-ILVO
3	FAIR & GDPR compliant digital personal data wallet	JIBE
4	Multimedia questionnaire generator	JIBE
5	DataU as GDPR compliant data sharing platform	JIBE
6	Handbook for implementation and replication of CSLs and BCIs	SFC
7	Citizen Science Labs	INCOMMON, ITC, HBK, VIC, CITTÀ DI TORINO, BFL, Rete delle Case del Quartiere di Torino, MoThess

8	Guidelines for Co-Designing Behaviour Change Interventions & Intervention Data and Insights	CSCP and coordinators	CSL
9	SPOON Academy for replication of CSLs	CSCP	
10	Policy recommendations package	AIT	
11	Citizen Science Lab monitoring toolkit	AIT	
12	SWOT analysis of existing tools and platforms for sharing food data	ITC	

SPOON’s C&D activities will support the uptake and understanding of results through tailored formats and messages aimed at (and developed with) specific audiences such as citizens, food system actors, scientific community, decisionmakers, policymakers, consumer associations, NGOs. Engaging dissemination formats such as info-packs, video tutorials, podcasts, and best practice books will help bridge the gap between project outputs and practical usability, considering the collaborative research approach of SPOON.

Key components of the exploitation strategy are the “Citizen Science Academy” and the “SPOON digital toolset”, which will support capacity-building and replication of SPOON methodologies and tools. Together, they form a core package of actionable project outputs designed to empower local actors and enable data-informed behaviour change. C&D efforts will play a central role in raising visibility and fostering engagement around both the Academy and the toolset. Dedicated campaigns, tailored content formats and targeted outreach activities will help attract relevant stakeholders (e.g. citizen groups, research communities, policymakers, public authorities, industry) and support their uptake and use during and beyond the project’s lifetime, both at local level through the CSLs (WP3-WP4) and more broadly at national and European scale, not only by disseminating their content, but also by supporting their practical adoption through targeted engagement with actors able to scale and replicate SPOON’s approach.

Finally, SPOON’s clustering activities and participation in key events will serve as a direct bridge between communication and exploitation. Through liaison with similar initiatives and the organisation of dedicated events (e.g., the “From SPOON to Policy” series), the project will actively position its results in broader communities of practice. This will help build synergies, identify new opportunities for replication, and foster uptake of SPOON outputs into future policies and initiatives.

2.4 TARGET GROUPS

Stakeholders are individuals or groups of people, institutions or companies that may be significantly affected, positively or negatively, by the success or failure of an intervention¹.

¹ European Commission. (2025, March 20). *Stakeholder analysis*. EXACT External Wiki. <https://wikis.ec.europa.eu/display/ExactExternalWiki/Stakeholder%2Banalysis>

SPOON engages a wide variety of stakeholders, reflecting the complex, multi-actor nature of food systems; the C&D strategy is designed to ensure that all the different target groups will be reached and engaged. The preliminary identification of target groups is based on the analysis included in the Grant Agreement (Section 2.2) and will be further developed under WP6 and within task T3.2 “Mapping of actors and value chains in food and related sectors in CSL regions”. These groups below represent both the co-creators and the potential adopters of SPOON’s results.

This list will be further developed and refined in the upcoming Deliverable D7.2 as well as through the stakeholder mapping and engagement activities led by PNO (WP6) and SFC (WP3), fully aligned with the evolving needs of the SPOON project.

Table 3. Target groups and objectives

Target group	Objective
Citizens and communities	Promote wide participation in the CSLs activities, increase knowledge and ability to interpret data, empower them to change their behaviours towards healthier and more sustainable food consumption thus take a leading role in the transformation of the food systems
Local and regional authorities related to the food system	Facilitate open dialogue and cooperation creating a favourable environment for CSLs
Civil society organisations and NGOs	Facilitate open dialogue and cooperation creating a favourable environment for CSLs
Industry actors and SME	Facilitate knowledge transfer to accelerate the innovation of the food system through evidence-based and data-driven grassroots actions
Research and academic institutions	Advance scientific knowledge and further exploit SPOON results in future research
Education and training providers	Addressing the increasing need for food science education and engaging, practice-based methods
Policymakers and public administrators	Promote the implementation of new transformative food system governance models, providing new insights and bottom-up, cross-actor inputs
Fellow EU-funded projects and networks	Promote close collaboration, knowledge sharing, engagement, new partnerships, advocacy

Professional press	Raise awareness and enhance understanding about food insecurity and the required transformation
Food influencers	Raise awareness and enhance understanding about food insecurity and the required transformation

2.5 KEY MESSAGES AT PROJECT LEVEL

Key messages are short, direct and easy-to-remember messages, specifically developed for each targeted stakeholder group. Identifying the correct key messages is crucial for shaping the communication products and actions and ensuring effective engagement with the specific targets.

During the SPOON Kick-Off meeting held in Wuppertal in March 2025, a co-creation exercise was organised with the whole consortium, asking them to develop some project-level key messages. This ensured a common understanding of the project driving the SPOON C&D effort by conveying the core concepts and ideas the project wants to communicate. These messages have been refined by ICONS and CSCP.

The challenge of facing such a variety of targets entails the need to create a series of key messages that communicate SPOON's core objectives. Blending specific keywords, messages and target audiences ensures the likelihood for SPOON to resonate with each audience.

In the table below, **messages at the project level are available, while in D7.2 will be included further refined key messages for each stakeholder group and for each CSL.**

Table 4. Refined key messages

Refined key messages	Target
Thanks to SPOON, tools will be developed to enable data-driven and inclusive decision-making along the value chain	General public, media
SPOON supports the transition to sustainable food behaviours through data-driven tools and citizen engagement	
With SPOON, eat the right food — and give food its right	
SPOON empowers citizens to lead the healthy food revolution and tackle food inequalities OR	

SPOON drives inclusive change towards a sustainable, healthy food future by actively engaging citizens

OR

SPOON addresses food inequalities by empowering citizens to achieve healthier lifestyles

2.6 CLUSTERING

Task T7.4 (“Clustering with other EU projects and JRC”), led by PNO, focuses on fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange with other EU-funded initiatives working on food system transformation, citizen science, behavioural change, and sustainable nutrition. This task will ensure that SPOON’s results are positioned within broader communities of practice and aligned with policy frameworks such as [FOOD 2030](#), [the Mission Soil](#), and the [Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems](#).

Although the clustering actions will intensify in the second year of the project, a first set of activities is already being planned:

- Identification of relevant sister projects under Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 (e.g. FOODMISSION, FOOD2030, GOVERNANCE, WIDERA, LIFE, Erasmus+).
- Establishment of direct contact with coordinators and communication managers to explore mutual synergies.
- Engagement with CLEVERFOOD’s FOOD2030 platform (<https://food2030.eu/>) to increase SPOON’s visibility and participate in collaborative actions.
- Planning of a dedicated series of multi-project policy events, titled “From SPOON to Policy”, to present project results to public authorities, networks and peer initiatives.
- Application to the Horizon Results Booster service to support joint dissemination strategy design and structured collaboration with relevant initiatives.

A preliminary list of projects of interest includes:

Table 5. Preliminary list of projects

Project	Focus	Programme
Data4Food2030	<u>Data economy for sustainable food systems</u>	<u>Horizon Europe, FOOD2030</u>
FOODITY	<u>Citizen-respectful data innovation in food and nutrition</u>	<u>Horizon Europe, FOOD2030</u>

FOODMISSION	<u>Citizens engaged as change-leaders for sustainable food systems</u>	<u>Horizon Europe, FOOD2030</u>
DRG4Food	<u>Fair European food register and citizen data sovereignty</u>	<u>Horizon Europe, FOOD2030</u>
TITAN	<u>Transparency and accountability in food systems</u>	<u>Horizon Europe, FOOD2030</u>
S3FOOD	<u>Smart sensors for food quality and efficiency</u>	<u>Horizon 2020</u>
PROTEIN	<u>Personalised nutrition and behavioural recommendations</u>	<u>Horizon 2020</u>
FNS-Cloud	<u>Integration of food and nutrition data infrastructures</u>	<u>Horizon 2020</u>

These and other relevant projects will be continuously monitored through tools like [WheesBee](#) and direct interaction with the European Commission. A more detailed clustering strategy and calendar of activities will be presented in D7.2, ensuring complementarity and mutual reinforcement across initiatives.

3 C&D MATERIALS AND FORMATS

Table 6 shows how each category identified through the preliminary stakeholder mapping exercise will be addressed by the project dissemination and communication activities. Dissemination content may be adapted and conveyed through formats and channels that will be deemed the most effective and impactful for the relevant target groups.

In this project, citizens are a central target audience which means the overall tone of voice will be informal and easy-to-understand; plain language and accessible style will be adopted to ensure content is comprehensible and engaging to the general public. Local communication and dissemination will be particularly important, as explained in the following chapters.

Table 6. Target group and C&D formats and channels

Target group	D&C formats	D&C channels
Citizens and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyer • Journalistic articles • Videos • News releases • Podcast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media • Media multipliers
Local and regional authorities related to the food system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyer • Videos • Infopacks/factsheets • Policy brief • Best practice book 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Events and conferences
Civil society organisations and NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyer • Videos • Infopacks/factsheets • Best practice book • EIP-AGRI practice abstracts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Events and conferences
Industry actors and SME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Infopacks/factsheets • Best practice book • Videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events and conferences • Social media • Scientific journals • Website
Research and academic institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Best practice book • Videos • Flyer • Podcast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Events and conferences
Education and training providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyer • Best practice book • Infopacks/factsheets • Policy brief/recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media • Media multipliers • Events and conferences
Policymakers and public administrators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyer • Podcast • Best practice book • Videos • Policy brief 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events and conferences • Social media • Website

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EIP-AGRI abstracts 	practice	
Fellow projects and networks	EU-funded and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press and news releases Journalistic articles Podcast EIP-AGRI abstracts 	practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Media multipliers

3.1 VISUAL IDENTITY

Having a visual identity is essential to keep coherence and consistency in the external communication. A visual identity consists of a logo complemented by a palette of colours as well as specific fonts. Developing a unique visual identity makes the project stand out among the others. The SPOON visual identity was developed through a brand personality assessment procedure executed with the coordinator; the results of this assessment served as the foundation of the project visual identity.

The key concepts of the visual are:

- Spoon as a symbol for mixing and bringing together diverse ideas and perspectives
- Idea of collaboration, co-design inclusivity and equality
- Colourful line that represents unity and fluidity

Figure 3. SPOON logo

Figure 4. Example of SPOON icons developed

The keywords that guided ICONS' process were:

- Community
- Empowering
- People
- Connection
- Support
- Co-design
- Accessibility
- Relatability

For the sake of completeness of the visual identity process and results, the present document also includes

Annex 1 – Brandbook which contains guidelines on how to use the project's logo and visual elements (font, colour palette etc). The visual identity rules and guidelines must be consistently applied across all communication and dissemination channels and formats, to ensure a cohesive and recognisable presence for the project. The Brandbook has been made available on the project's repository so that it can be consulted by all partners.

In order to raise the visibility of SPOON, all the communication and dissemination materials will contain the logo. To acknowledge the EU funding and branding, the EU flag and a reference

text must accompany the logo.

3.2 CHANNELS

3.2.1 Website and landing page

The SPOON project website can be considered as the main communication channel, and it provides the principal interface towards all target audiences. It provides the key information about the project, its objectives, expected outcomes and achievements.

The website will be launched in M8 along with the communication kit that includes a project video, a project PPT, a flyer and a roll-up. This will allow ICONS to meet the milestone as per the Grant Agreement. At this date, the project website will be available at **spoonproject.eu** thus replacing the landing page that was created at M2 to provide an online project reference and contact point ad interim (see figure below).

Figure 5. SPOON landing page

The website will be designed, implemented and managed by ICONS to be user-friendly and accessible. The website will feature project updates and provide details about events and initiatives. In addition, it will contain a reproduction of Zenodo, acting as a repository for the resources open to the public, including reports and public deliverables.

The project website will be structured to cover the key aspects of the project and to encourage navigation across sections. The website will feature the following sections:

- Home
- What is SPOON?
- How SPOON works

- Pilots
- News
- Events
- Resources

Table 7. Accountability website

Accountability	<p>The SPOON website is developed and managed by ICONS, that is responsible for creating and regularly updating its content.</p> <p>In adherence to the General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will be kept confidential. ICONS will act as the Data Controller and will be responsible for handling all sensitive data provided by registered users during online registration.</p> <p>All SPOON partners are required to inform ICONS about key developments, initiatives, events, news.</p>
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3.2.2 Partners' corporate channels

All partners' channels are essential to support the project outreach. SPOON partners are strongly encouraged to share official content through their website, social media, newsletters, etc. ICONS has identified a contact point for C&D activities for each partner and will share with them the editorial contents developed throughout the project for possible uptake. Partners' websites and social media channels are listed in [Annex 3](#).

3.2.3 Social media (LinkedIn and Instagram)

The use of social media will enable SPOON to reach a higher visibility of its objectives, results and activities. **Social media will boost the outreach and engagement** of the project's communication activities, as it will allow to touch base with audiences that are difficult to reach through other conventional project channels.

SPOON established its social media presence on Instagram and LinkedIn. The two social networks convey the project's messages, which are adapted in terms of graphic layout and messages, to the main audiences of those platforms.

The **LinkedIn company page** is mainly dedicated to a professional audience intended as: stakeholders, policy makers and industries. It was opened in January 2025 (M2) and will be maintained throughout the duration of the project and kept open beyond the project. The editorial plan includes regular posts to maintain the public's attention regarding SPOON's activities and main results, among which are public deliverables, scientific publications, details and follow-up news about the progress made by the project, and events.

Figure 6. SPOON LinkedIn header

In the **Instagram channel**, the language will be adapted to a broader audience exploitation, with particular attention to simplifying “higher” concepts without trivialising them.

While more professional content will still be shared, this channel has been chosen to give relevance to products such as social media campaigns - intended to deepen and explain SPOON, its aim or results-, vox pop videos, informal work-in-progress material, and user generated content produced by ICONS and the CSL in the framework of their activities in the field.

Figure 7. SPOON Instagram page

The official hashtag **#spoon_eu** was launched during the online kick-off in December 2024, to help monitor conversations about the project. The official hashtag is monitored by ICONS as part of the impact assessment campaign which will be carried out throughout the project (see chapter

Monitoring and impact assessment methodology).

A YouTube account will be set-up in July 2025 (M8) to host the project’s presentation video and the project’s further video production such as the video interviews working as a public repository.

Table 8. Accountability social media

Accountability	<p>ICONS will be responsible for activities like posting, following and interacting with EU projects, initiatives and other relevant stakeholders, as well as monitoring outreach.</p> <p>All partners are encouraged to contribute by following SPOON accounts, reposting or sharing content, and inviting their contacts to follow the page. It is recommended to tag SPOON and use the official hashtag #spoon_eu.</p>
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3.2.4 Media multipliers

External media multipliers will be used to disseminate contents of general interest produced by SPOON. News multipliers are portals and websites that relay scientific and non-scientific news and information. They serve as gateways for journalists, media, researchers and the general public. ICONS has built a network of news multipliers that enjoy large audiences in Europe. Some outlets focus on specific topics while others are managed by the European Commission, or they are related to it. Key multipliers include: [EU Agenda](#), [Alpha Galileo](#), [Science X](#), and [Youris](#). The [youris.com](#) portal is a major integrated audiovisual and news platform about European science, innovation, policy and research for web, social and TV media. It is owned and managed by ICONS, and it is continuously updated with news, journalistic articles and video news releases (VNR) on European Research and Innovation. The portal covers a large spectrum of research domains and has proven an excellent multiplier for content generated from the outcomes of hundreds of European-funded projects.

SPOON journalistic articles and interviews will be published on both the project website and on youris.com, hence highly increasing the content’s visibility. ICONS has set up syndication agreements with some multipliers to receive statistics on the performance of distributed content. One example is the number of users who have read the news posted. These statistics are used for the communication & dissemination monitoring and impact assessment activity that ICONS conducts. Products to be distributed will include journalistic articles, info-packs, the best practice book, video interviews, press and news releases.

Table 9. Accountability media multipliers

Accountability	<p>ICONS is in charge of exploiting multipliers and Youris. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.</p>
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3.3 DISSEMINATION FORMATS

Within SPOON, ICONS will oversee the production of content-specific D&C formats and will take care of their distribution through dedicated channels, thus maximising impact in terms of awareness, acceptance and uptake. The following materials and formats will be developed:

Table 10. Dissemination formats, KPI and targets

Dissemination format	KPI	Target groups
Communication kit	1 leaflet, 1 roll-up, 1 presentation video, 1 project PPT	All
Info-packs and factsheets	8 in total	Municipalities; industry; research; policymakers; fellow consortia; education
Policy brief	1 with recommendations	Policymakers
Best practice book	1	Citizens; municipalities; research; policymakers; fellow consortia; education
EIP-AGRI practice abstract	6	Industry; fellow consortia
Scientific publications	7	Industry
Video tutorial of digital dashboard	1	Citizens; municipalities; industry; education

3.3.1 Communication kit

The communication kit will be completed by M8 (July 2025), providing partners with professional quality material necessary to promote the project. The kit will include a leaflet/flyer, roll-up banner/poster, PowerPoint presentation and a project video tailored for a broader audience. The project video will have subtitles in all pilots' languages to provide local partners with the opportunity to share and use it in local C&D activities.

Resources from the communication kit will support project communication by allowing SPOON partners to use them as a hook to engage with stakeholders, particularly when

participating in events. It will contain all the information stakeholders need to know regarding the project. All visual materials will be available in electronic format for downloading.

Table 11. Accountability communication kit

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of creating this content. The coordinator/other relevant partners provide feedback/approval. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.3.2 Infopacks and factsheets

Factsheets/info-packs come as synthetic reports. These are designed for the professional community to learn about technical insights, solutions and methodologies developed and used by the project. They are formats that need to be targeted to specific audiences, according to the project needs.

This format allows to package technical achievements and findings into a visually attractive and easy-to-access document. The specific contents will be taken from the public deliverables and scientific publications produced by the project or by key output of the project.

Their format makes them particularly suitable for distribution at scientific and technical events. Moreover, they will also be made available for download from the project website and will be distributed to specific key stakeholders' groups.

Some content has been deemed interesting by ICONS team and might be chosen to be further develop in this format. The following list of topics, timeline and targets is preliminary and might change during the project lifecycle according to project's needs:

Table 12. Possible topics for infopacks

Topic	WP	Timeline	Target
Barriers and drivers to sustainable and healthy food consumption	WP1	M24, after Deliverable	Research communities; policymakers; industries and professionals in food sectors; local/national food agencies
Capacity building programme	WP6	M44	Municipalities; community leaders; education and

			training institutes; CSOs; NGOs
Presenting the benefits of the toolset	WP2	M23, after testing	Industry and professionals in food sector; policymakers; research communities
Behavioural change interventions/CSLs results (one per each CSL)	WP3/WP4	M26, after D4.1	Research communities; municipalities; local/national food agencies; policymakers; living labs
Engagement methodologies and replications suggestions from each CSL	WP4	M44, after D4.2	Research communities; municipalities; CSOs; NGOs; education and training institutes; living labs

Table 13. Accountability infopacks

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of producing this content with technical input from partners. Coordinator/relevant partners have to provide feedback/approval. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.3.3 Policy brief

One policy brief will be developed by technical partners for policymakers and local authorities towards the end of the project.

The policy brief will be elaborated starting from the output D6.5 “Policy recommendations package” due at M48. These recommendations will explain how Citizen Science will drive food system transformation. The content will be adapted and put in a nicer format. The policy brief will be available on the website and will be disseminated.

Table 14. Accountability policy brief

Accountability	Technical partners of WP6 will provide input for the policy brief. ICONS is in charge of producing an improved layout. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.3.4 Best practice book

The final Best practice book (BPB) will be produced at the end of the project to disseminate the achievements and innovations of the project. Some of the content might highlight the results of the CSLs (stemming from D4.1 and D4.2 and D3.2) as well as comparing best practices explained in D1.3 changing the format and thus making the content more appropriate for a non-professional audience.

The book will be elaborated starting from the outputs of the project in collaboration with the relevant technical partners. It will be available on the website.

Table 15. Accountability Best Practice Book

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of producing the BPB with technical input from partners. Coordinator/relevant partners have to provide feedback/approval. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.3.5 EIP-AGRI practice abstracts

Practice abstracts refer to the format defined by EIP-AGRI (Agricultural European Innovation Partnership) for communication on projects, activities and results to facilitate knowledge flows on innovative and practice-oriented projects from the beginning to the end of the project. The use of this format also enables farmers, advisors, researchers and all other actors across the EU to contact each other.

Relevant outcomes will be used to produce 2 groups of EIP-AGRI practice abstracts during the project (first group with 3 EIP-AGRI delivered at M18 and second group with 3 EIP-AGRI delivered at M48) and they will be published in this format to reach specific stakeholders. This format is the most suited one to communicate technical information and recommendations and thus reaching specific stakeholders within the agriculture sector. EIP-AGRI connects organisations, administrations, researchers, entrepreneurs and practitioners who can share knowledge and information about agriculture and rural policy.

Technical partners will provide content, and ICONS will proofread and give support checking that the visual identity is respected. The final version will be available on the EU CAP network, and disseminated through SPOON channels.

Table 16. Accountability EIP-AGRI

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of coordinating the production of six EIP-AGRI with technical input from partners. Coordinator/relevant partners have to provide feedback/approval. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.3.6 Scientific publications

The project is expected to generate scientific results worth to be disseminated in scientific conferences and published in open-access journals.

Seven SPOON papers will feature the most relevant and interesting project's achievements. Technical partners will publish the papers and news about the release of SPOON's scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be shared via the project website and social media channels.

Table 17. Accountability scientific publications

Accountability	Technical partners are in charge of publishing on relevant technical publications. ICONS is in charge of further disseminating them through website, social media etc. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.3.7 Video tutorial for digital dashboard

One video tutorial will be prepared in order to further promote the digital dashboard/toolset, its benefits for end-users as well as its user-friendliness.

The content will be decided together with relevant technical partners and ICONS will develop the video and disseminate it through the website and social media channels.

Table 18. Accountability video tutorial

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of producing a video tutorial after the SPOON toolset is ready to be used. Relevant partners will provide content and/or feedback/approval. Partners have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.4 EDITORIAL FORMATS

This table contains a description of the editorial products that will be produced during the project and associated targets.

Table 19. Editorial formats summary

Format	KPI	Target
News and press releases	10	Citizens; media
Journalistic articles	3	Citizens; media
Podcast	4 episodes	Citizens; media

3.4.1 News and press releases

SPOON press and news releases are meant to draw the stakeholders' and the public's attention towards the project, the progress made, and the results achieved.

Press releases are particularly effective when it comes to communicating the project's main achievements and key milestones, like the release of a scientific paper or a technical deliverable.

News releases, on the other hand, have an informal structure and they use plain language thus they are easily read by the public. They are usually published on the project website to communicate news about the project, its features and its work which are all worth bringing to the attention of the SPOON community despite not being "breaking news". A news release will be produced, for example, to explain an innovative concept developed by the project or on background information on a project activity.

News releases are particularly effective when informing of the participation of some members of the SPOON partnership to external events to present their latest project findings or achievement.

Both the press releases and the news releases will be published on the project website and, whenever deemed newsworthy, they will be distributed to external online resources and news multipliers.

Consortium members are encouraged to actively publish and post on their own distribution channels and external media news about their project.

Table 20. Accountability news and press releases

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of producing news and press releases. Partners have to let ICONS know when activities unfold and have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.4.2 Journalistic articles

Independent journalistic articles and/or interviews will be written by professional journalists. They will cover topics linked to SPOON with an angle suitable to reach a wider audience.

Articles will be published via the project website. Moreover, they will be distributed to the public at a European and global level using different multipliers or media platforms, namely EU Agenda, AlphaGalileo, Youris.com and Phys.org and other platforms which will be indicated as relevant. Social media channels will promote articles when released.

Journalistic articles to inform and stimulate interest among the public about the topics covered by the project. They will serve to present a technical project like SPOON to a laymen's audience by using understandable language and messages. These formats work well to raise public awareness, the project's key ideas and, ultimately, contribute to social acceptance of results.

These are preliminary ideas for journalistic articles that might be changed according to needs of the project:

- Food insecurity and how to tackle it.
- Sustainable and health food patterns and consumption.
- Participative approaches as tools to develop citizenship (CSL and BCI).
- Particular interesting local story/experience of one of the CSLs

Table 21. Accountability journalistic articles

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of producing journalistic articles. Partners have to collaborate with professional journalist and have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.4.3 Podcast episodes

4 podcast episodes will be released throughout the project when it is considered to be more appropriate and, possibly, in occasion of other activities, (local) events or editorial products. If of interest, some of the participants of CSLs might be invited to speak in the podcast to also ensure their commitment and engagement.

Topics for the podcast might come from the activities and behavioural interventions done at the CSLs. ICONS and relative technical partners will jointly discuss the content, the format and the logistics. The discussion will involve partners that already have a podcast channel so as to develop a link with the podcast series they already produce. The episodes will be promoted on social media and will be available through the website as well.

Table 22. Accountability podcast

Accountability	ICONS is in charge of producing podcast episodes. Coordinator/relevant partners have to provide technical input. Partners have to collaborate and have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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3.5 EVENTS

SPOON partners will participate in networking and clustering events to raise the project's visibility within the stakeholder community.

Reaching out to the stakeholders by attending events in person can effectively multiply opportunities of interaction between the project consortium and their professional target audience.

Beyond the local events linked to SPOON's CSLs as presented in the GA, based on their experience with other initiatives (like [BREADCRUMB](#)), the consortium has also mapped some additional relevant events considering SPOON's KPIs (10 external events, 2 EU-level workshops at each CSL, 2 webinars, 1 final event). This is presented in the following table:

Partners will keep track of the upcoming networking and clustering events, and they will inform the rest of the partnership about their wish to participate on behalf of SPOON. Events attendance will be monitored through a regular communication flow happening within the consortium and updates will be collected by ICONS on a six-month basis through a dedicated template. Examples of events include conferences, fairs, workshops, roundtables, brokerage events on project related topics, etc. The project's communication products will be distributed at these events to aid the partners in promoting the project. The partners' attendance to such events will be featured in the project website and in the social media channels to ensure they get the appropriate visibility.

Table 23. Events list with KPI

Event	Description/Relevance
European Week of Regions and Cities (Oct 2025)	Opportunity to connect with regional and local authorities involved in food policy and urban innovation. Potential venue for SPOON's "From SPOON to Policy" events.
Food2030 Conference (next edition TBD, likely late 2025)	Flagship event to showcase results from F2F-related projects. SPOON can present synergies on data-driven behavioural change and citizen engagement.
Joint webinar with FOODITY / DRG4Food (TBD)	Focused session on digital tools, data governance, and citizen sovereignty in food environments.
CleverFood Community Assembly (Q4 2025 or Q1 2026)	Great occasion to present SPOON tools and methods to a curated group of policy stakeholders, researchers and practitioners.

EAT@Home (EAT Forum) (June 2026)	International stage to present SPOON's approach to healthier diets, with high policy and media visibility.
ZeroW final event (if matched) (Q4 2025)	Collaboration opportunity with a project working on reducing food waste. Alignment via citizen science methods.

Table 24. Accountability events attendance

Accountability	All partners should contribute to attend events and presents SPOON. PNO/ICONS are in charge of coordinating the organization of some events. Partners have to collaborate and have to share with their own network to contribute to a higher outreach.
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4 MANAGEMENT OF C&D ACTIVITIES

4.1 SECRETARIAT

Dissemination will be performed at different geographical levels:

- At European and International level managed by WP7 leader (ICONS) and by the project coordinator (CSCP) supported by all the partners.
- At National/Regional/Local level managed by the entire consortium through the partners' already existing communication assets and towards their communities in their countries.

To guarantee the continuous interaction between EU/international and local dissemination and a coherent communication flow between partners and the Communication and Dissemination secretariat, a WP7 mailing list has been set up. Each partner will appoint a maximum of two contact people as main interface for WP7 activities. In particular, the contact persons of the partners responsible for the CSLs are called the Local C&D Desks and will act as the main reference for the local CSL Communities in cooperation with WP3 and WP4 leaders.

SPOON Dissemination and Communication Secretariat represents the central office coordinating all contacts

towards EU stakeholder communities and other dissemination and communication target audiences.

European communication will be centrally managed by the SPOON Secretariat, led by ICONS, and by the project coordinator (CSCP) by using appropriate channels and tools according to the different targets. The Secretariat also represents the main interface with the other WP leaders for the transfer of project contents and results aimed at dissemination and communication. The Secretariat will directly report to the project coordinator and will play an active role, informing and involving the partners in all on-going dissemination and communication activities. The C&D Secretariat will work in close cooperation with the other project partners and with the CSL. Each partner shall also be committed to addressing its dissemination networks and communities to further promote the project, thus ensuring maximum visibility towards their existing communities and contribute to creating impacts both at local and EU level.

The strategic objectives of the SPOON Secretariat at European level are:

- Implement a Dissemination and Communication Plan according to an effective communication and dissemination strategy and guarantee public and professional/technical coverage of the project achievements in view of enabling widespread replication and uptake of the project's outcomes at EU level.
- Communicate benefits and usability of the developed SPOON solutions (SPOON toolset) and methodologies (Citizen Science Labs and Behaviour Change interventions) to all relevant target groups and the public at large and actively engage with European communities of stakeholders (including citizens).
- Support optimal conditions and solutions for the replication and exploitation of the project outcomes by consolidating the project visibility among stakeholders and communities at European, national, regional and local level (supporting WP6)
- Interact with the Local C&D Desks of the CSLs to define local strategies exploiting both already existing local channels and tools as well as the communication assets specifically set up to ensure the wide participation of local/regional/national stakeholders and citizens in the project and enable the regular flow of information from the Local Desks to the Secretariat and vice versa to guarantee the coverage, distribution and impact of information at local and European level.

The C&D Secretariat is responsible for:

- Project visual identity (logo, icons, graphic elements and images, templates) and guidelines on how to use them, to ensure consistency in communication
- Production of communication and dissemination materials (short presentation video, brochure etc)
- Design and implementation of the project website and social media strategy
- Production of articles and press releases that will be distributed to information multipliers and online media
- Support the organisation of events, webinars and workshops.

4.2 LOCAL

The Local C&D Desks will be the main contact points to implement local stakeholders and citizens engagement campaigns. The Local C&D Desks will oversee the local C&D strategy definition, including, identification of appropriate channels, messages and specific social media and communication formats to foster engagement. ICONS, as lead C&D Secretariat, will support the local CSLs to develop their own C&D local strategy.

The Local Desks will actively support the collaboration between the C&D Secretariat and each CSL: this collaboration will facilitate the deployment of the citizens' and stakeholders' engagement strategy (in relation with WP3) at local level in a very effective and customised way. **While in this D7.1, the strategy for local C&D desk is briefly outlined in the present chapter, in the second version of the Communication and Dissemination plan (D7.2 due at M18) a more detailed description of their C&D strategy will be outlined.** This will include for each CSL a short description, their key stakeholders, local media and channels that can be used and a preliminary plan for local events to be organised.

Specifically, each Local Desk will:

- Provide local contents to the C&D Secretariat for EU diffusion
- Guarantee distribution of the project's contents (press releases, events, videos, flyers, etc.) at local level, translating content in local language
- Organize and manage local engagement (citizens and stakeholders)
- Produce short videos and photos to capture local stories and contents to be distributed via the project online channels (web and social media)
- Maximise outreach towards other close local areas
- Track and monitor C&D activities at local level

Table 25. Accountability local desks

Accountability	Responsible of C&D local desks should contribute to ensure outreach and engagement at local level. ICONS are in charge of coordinating the C&D activities, but local partners are ultimately responsible for implementing the activities.
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4.3 CONTINUOUS REPORTING

All the partners will be asked to report on their individual dissemination and communication activities through a reporting template that will be sent to all the contacts of the consortium, including the representatives of C&D.

This regular monitoring will contribute to measure the outreach and feedback to the dissemination and communication strategy of SPOON. These activities may include participation at events (local, European, global level), publication of news and articles,

appearance in TV or radio shows, campaigns on social media. The reporting templates are

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included in

Figure 10. Brandbook

Annex 2 – Reporting template. The partners’ continuous reporting will be included in the periodic reporting to the European Commission.

4.4 RESPONSIBILITY IN THE CONSORTIUM

To ensure that EU-wide communication activities can reach out to the mentioned stakeholders and the general public in order to maximise the impact and the exploitation of SPOON results, full cooperation needs to be established between the Communication and Dissemination Leader (ICONS), the Exploitation Leader (PNO), the CSL coordinator (SFC), and the rest of the consortium.

There are strong interactions between the project dissemination and communication, illustrated in the current document, and the partners’ local activities, especially with stakeholders and professional audiences.

Therefore, **full cooperation from the rest of the team and consortium is expected**. In fact, all the project partners are expected to cooperate by participating in webinars, direct interviews and questionnaires, which will be facilitated by PNO, to gather information necessary to define the project KERs and the most suitable exploitation strategies.

Role and responsibility of ICONS, the project coordinator and all the other member of the SPOON consortium can be summarised according to the following scheme:

Table 26. Consortium accountability in communication and dissemination

Partner	Role
ICONS – WP7 leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leading and coordinating CD activities • Coordinate with PNO to ensure synergies with exploitation • Developing SPOON visual identity • Designing, updating and maintaining the project website • Providing official templates and creating communication kit • Producing content to be published on website together with the contributions of partners • Monitoring the impact of C&D material through dedicated indexes
CSCP - Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validating the C&D strategy • Provide feedback/approval on materials and contents released (such as website, info-packs, leaflet, podcast etc) • Provide guidance on the status of the project to ensure C&D material give visibility to specific aspects of the project
SFC – WP3 leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of stakeholders • Implementing a common framework for CSLs • Supporting CSLs activities
PNO – WP6 leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining the exploitation strategy and upscaling • Ensuring the alignment of target groups, KERs strategy and pathways with C&D strategy and actions
CSL coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborating with ICONS to develop specific local C&D plans for CSLs • Keeping ICONS informed of relevant local events, activities and similar
All consortium members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide input to create SPOON materials and channels (such as website, info-packs, leaflet, podcast etc) • Keeping ICONS informed when relevant progress is made • Providing ICONS with the list of events and publications they will be attending on behalf of SPOON

- Boosting SPOON's presence on social media
- Mobilizing networks and connections for wider outreach and promotion of SPOON

5 MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

The monitoring and assessment of the SPOON C&D activities is pivotal for the project. This provides a quantitative estimate of the impacts generated across the targeted stakeholder groups in terms of awareness and acceptance. In particular, high acceptance levels are a necessary requirement for market uptake of the developed solutions.

ICONS has developed a solid monitoring and impact assessment methodology² focused on the distribution of contents and the engagement mechanisms of all project communication activities and across all considered channels. The approach is based on a number of indicators that can be aggregated or singled-out in a flexible way to enable the analysis of each component and its determinants. These indicators represent the performance metrics of SPOON and have been developed to be:

- **Measurable:** they can be represented numerically and analysed over time to identify trends, best practices and pitfalls.
- **Easy to understand and to be used by project's partners,** to ensure exploitation of the resulting analysis.
- **Repeatable:** they can be used and collected in a consistent way along project's execution.
- **Available:** sources are always accessible and available.
- **Timely:** they are made available every time a new communication or engagement effort is undertaken.
- **Reliable:** they are drawn from trusted sources in the online analytics world.
- **Insightful:** they provide knowledge around the effectiveness of the communication and engagement effort.

The monitoring of the adopted indicators and the assessment of the generated impacts (also via qualitative feedback from the direct exchange with the stakeholders) are continuously performed over the course of the project. This enables ICONS not only to monitor SPOON communication impacts, but also to take corrective actions and improve performances and maximise impacts if needed.

The following section provides a concise description of the methodology developed and implemented by ICONS. A more detailed description will be provided in D7.5 (M48).

5.1 MONITORING METHODOLOGY

The monitoring methodology is based on outreach and engagement indicators calculated from data collected via dedicated web analytics and software tools. Outreach indicators measure online and offline communication reach with the aim of strengthening the impact on

² Folco, G., Gaboardi, E., Lischetti, S., Martinoli, M., Mazzolo, G., & Schmid, E. (2022). *Two new tools for science communication assessment: The community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants* (Version 1) [Working paper]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985584>

awareness. They provide an estimate of the number of people who came across a specific content. Engagement indicators measure the number of interactions that stakeholders made with the content they came in contact with. They give an estimate of the project acceptance.

In the table below, the tools that will be employed by the ICONS team are showed. The sums of the indicators give the publications total outreach and total engagement values at the time of the data collection. The outreach and engagement values of each channel are calculated with different approaches (based e.g. on the total amount of webpages viewed or the time spent on them) but by using the same tools. Finally, ad-hoc indicators have been developed to estimate the outreach and engagement values generated by events such as conferences, webinars etc. based on the audience size.

Table 27. ICONS' monitoring tools and parameters

Activity	Tool	Parameter
Website	MATOMO	Pageviews, visitors, most viewed pages
News dissemination	TALKWALKER and distribution platforms data	Pageviews, visitors, most viewed pages
Social media	LinkedIn Stats, Twitter Analytics, Facebook insights	Number of post, viewers, external outreach
Online videos	YouTube Studio	Number of views, external embedding
Webinars	Gotowebinar	Registrations, attendance, engagement of participants

5.1.1 ICONS' engagement indexes

Outreach and engagement indicators are not sufficient to assess the evolution of the acceptance level. The former only provide an estimate of audience size, not its interest level. The latter describe the interest and overall impacts on a community but should be read in conjunction with outreach to draw relevant conclusions on engagement. To this aim, a composite indicator is needed.

ICONS studied a series of indices able to quantify the interest of a community in specific content³. With specific reference to contents distribution, the following indices are to be accounted for:

³ For more information, please visit: Folco Giuliana et al (2022) «Two new tools for science communication assessment: the community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants». Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6985584.

Figure 8. ICONS' indexes

Engagement can be regarded as the state in which stakeholders interact actively with the project itself and its outcomes. The ability to assess the effectiveness of communication and engagement is therefore crucial.

To track and analyse stakeholders' engagement, ICONS has developed a methodology based on continuous monitoring of (i) the distribution of a project's content; and (ii) the engagement mechanisms of all project communication activities, across all the channels considered. This activity tracks the number of visualizations of and interactions with a project's content.

Outreach indicators: they assess the size of the audience reached by the content conveyed to strengthen target stakeholders' awareness. Outreach indicators are basic indices that on their own do not provide a complete picture of a project's communication effectiveness. They rather serve as a starting point for further analysis.

Engagement indicators: they help understand how effective a project's content is in generating interest and boosting acceptance from target stakeholders. Engagement metrics measure if and how stakeholders engage with the content, via e.g. online interactions. They are a quite powerful tool for assessing the effectiveness of the communication campaigns performed.

These two indicators have been integrated creating a composite engagement index for each area; the results are the following indexes that are used for all communication activities developed within an EU-funded project.

Outreach and engagement indicators are defined for the five areas covering typical communication activities carried out by research projects. Indicators are presented as aggregated quantities but can also be calculated for individual or a subset of websites, social media channels, publications, events etc.

The main indices developed by the project will be the Publication Engagement Index (PEI), the Social Engagement Index (SEI) and the Website Engagement Index (WEI). This latter indicator is calculated as

$$WEI_{norm} = \frac{ew}{ow} \times 100 \times \frac{100}{WEI_{95}^{\circ}}$$

Figure 9. Equation

where ow and ew are the website outreach and engagement indicators, respectively. The indices for the other areas — Social media Engagement Index (SEI), and Publication Engagement Index (PEI) are defined in a similar way.

In addition, the project may produce further monitoring and evaluation indexes of the project's communication and dissemination activities. These additional indices could monitor the engagement generated by participation in events, the outreach and engagement produced by the newsletter, or the engagement achieved by webinars. The production of these indices will depend on the activities the project will undertake and will be evaluated at a later stage of progress of the activities.

For consistency and ease of comparison, all indices are normalized on a 0–100 scale, where higher values reflect stronger engagement. The normalization benchmarks are based on ICONS' own project portfolio.

5.1.2 Timeline

This timeline covers the main activities for WP7 from the beginning until M18 when the second version of this Deliverable is due. The first months focus on setting up the visual identity, social media accounts, website and other outreach materials.

Table 28. Timeline of activities

When	What	Lead
M2-M3	Visual identity development, social media accounts, ppt and Word templates	ICONS
M3	Landing page development	ICONS
M6	D7.1 Communication and dissemination plan	ICONS
M8	Communication kit (roll-up, video, leaflet) + Website fully operational [MS2]	ICONS
M10-12	First article	ICONS
M10-M12	Setting up the strategy for local communication	ICONS
M18	D7.2 Communication and dissemination v2 including clustering activities	ICONS

6 CONCLUSIONS

This Deliverable outlines the overall C&D strategy of SPOON project.

The first chapter delves into the C&D strategy focusing on the key messages at project level and a preliminary mapping of relevant stakeholder groups. The main groups are citizens, municipalities and research communities therefore the objectives of the SPOON C&D strategy focus on promoting wide participation of citizens into SPOON activities as well as facilitate cooperation and make the knowledge available to them. In doing so, the C&D strategy complements the overall objectives of SPOON project to:

- Develop an analytical framework and increase understanding of factors influencing healthy and sustainable food consumption;
- Implement Citizen Science Labs (CSLs) and Behaviour Change Interventions (BCI) with citizens and food stakeholders to collect, visualise and interpret data on consumers' consumption behaviours and their local food purchasing and consumption environments;
- Create and deploy the SPOON digital toolset that includes a multimedia questionnaire generator and a personal data wallet to enable data collection and analysis (citizen science);
- Establish a GDPR-compliant data governance framework focusing on privacy, data sharing, and interoperability;
- Produce guidelines and a capacity-building programme for citizen science and consumer behaviour change projects aiming to exploit, replicate and accelerate project learnings, insights and results
- Draft policy recommendations to enhance data-driven policies through better use of citizen data, digital tools, and cross-sector collaboration.

The second chapter instead presents a short description of all the C&D channels and formats that have been defined in the strategy:

- the website, social media and the multipliers will be important to ensure the maximum visibility amongst all the target groups and to serve as an entry point/hook,
- the dissemination formats will be adapted according to the stakeholders that will be prioritised tailoring the content of info-packs, EIP-AGRI, videos and other formats.
- journalistic articles and press releases will instead reach a more general audience.

As explained in the last chapters, while ICONS is responsible of the production, technical partners are responsible not only to provide feedback on scientific correctness but also are called to activate their networks.

The next steps of C&D include:

- monitoring activities to ensure content outreach and engagement with the project,
- assessing its impact on target audiences following ICONS' methodology,
- production of communication kit (video, flyer, poster) and website to be distributed to partners,
- drafting Deliverable D7.2 with more detailed local C&D plans.

7 ANNEX 1 – BRANDBOOK

Here is presented the table of content of the brandbook of SPOON. It explains the rules of the correct use of the visual identity, and it has been distributed amongst partners.

February 2025

Version 1.0

BRAND GUIDELINES

01. PROJECT ESSENCE	3	Logotype minimum sizes	9	04. ICONS	17
Project essence	4	Logotype variation	10		
The spoon identity concept	5	Logos and background pairing	11	05. TYPOGRAPHY	19
		Photographic background	13	Official font	20
02. LOGOTYPE	6	03. COLOR PALETTE	14	Local communication font	21
Logotype	7	Color use guidelines	16	Greek glyphs	22
Safe space	8				

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Figure 10. Brandbook

8 ANNEX 2 – REPORTING TEMPLATE

Below the Excel template to be used by partners, especially local C&D, to report their C&D activities. There is one Excel respectively per Communication, Dissemination and Scientific Publications.

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES: List the dissemination activities carried out in the context of SPOON project. Here you can list the events of interest and then indicate in the "Status" column, if you end up going or not. You can write directly in this file whenever needed, This will be especially needed for each Reporting period								
Partner	Dissemination activity name	Where?	What?	Date	Who?	Why?	Status	Estimated number of
Choose your organisation from the list	Type the title of the activity/event. You can add a hyperlink if available.	Indicate if the event is online or in presence or hybrid	Choose the type of dissemination activity from the list. Please note that: - External meetings do not include the project meetings. - Clustering activities are those with cluster networks. - Collaborations with EU funded projects are any type of joint event not included in clustering activities. - When choosing Other, please specify the activity in the section 'Why'.	DD/MM/YY	Choose the most appropriate target audience from the list. If more target audiences were addressed, please add as many lines as necessary.	Insert a description of the activity, max 200 characters spaces included.	Choose the status of the dissemination activity from the list. For possible future activities, please mark them as 'Ongoing' and provide more details to ICONS via email when available, it helps us to promote the activity on social networks.	Please include here the estimated number of people you disseminated the project to. This is necessary to ICONS to monitor the engagement generated by events. This number will be included in the monitoring activity of the project.
This is just an example	ICONS Energy cluster to reduce energy poverty.	In presence	Clustering activity	25/04/2025	Policy-makers and authorities (international) EU institutions	The event was organised by the energy cluster for renewable energy and included 5 projects. Every project presented its solutions and distributed some informative materials. The event was mostly addressed to policy makers and institutions to improve the current policies.	Delivered	60
1	BFL CS4Health Conferentie	In presence, Zurich		06/11/2025			Of interest	
2	BFL ECS Collaboration Sessions	Online		04/02/2025			Of interest	
3	FOSSNET conference	Oxford (by invitation only)	Conference	25/03/2025			Of interest	
4	START conference	Copenhagen	Conference	29/04/2025			Of interest	
5	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact - G	Milan		TBD			Of interest	
6	Free from food expo	Vienna	Conference	17-18/06/2025			Of interest	
7	ITC Agra2025	Slovenia	Other	23/08/2025	Civil society (international)	Agra Fair is a major international agriculture and food fair showcasing innovations in farming, food processing, sustainability, and agribusiness, attracting industry experts, farmers, citizens, and policymakers	Of interest	100.000 visitors per year

Figure 11. Excel for dissemination activities

9 ANNEX 3 – PROJECT PARTNERS ONLINE CHANNELS

The website and social media channels of the project partners are listed in table:

Table 29. List of partners' websites and social media

Partner	Partner website	Partner social media/other channels
ICONS	https://www.icons.it/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/iconsinnovation/ Spotify: https://open.spotify.com/show/77bNzW08rbiGbcSQJThWRs YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCaXtFrYmQ13D1zp8AeCcaWQ

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/ICONSinnovation/
CSCP	https://www.cscp.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/collaborating-centre-on-sustainable-consumption-and-production-cscp/ • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/scpcentre • X: https://x.com/scp_centre
PNO	https://www.pnoconsultants.com/es/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/pno-consultants-spain/ • X: https://x.com/PNOconsultants • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@PNOConsultant
EV ILVO	https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/ilvo/ • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@ILVO.vlaanderen • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/ILVOvlaanderen • X: https://x.com/ILVOvlaanderen
AIT	https://www.ait.ac.at/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/austrian-institute-of-technology/ • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/AITtomorrow2day • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/aittomorrow2day • YouTube: https://www.facebook.com/AITtomorrow2day • X: https://x.com/AITtomorrow2day
SFC	https://scienceforchange.eu/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X: https://twitter.com/SciencefChange

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/scienceforchange/ • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/science-for-change • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@scienceforchange • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100075987725443
INCOMMON	https://www.incommon.gr/en/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/incommongr/ • Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/@ncommon-innovativecommunity5402 • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/incommon.gr/ • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/incommongr/
ITC	https://itc-cluster.com/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovation-technology-cluster/ • X: https://x.com/ITCcluster
HoC	https://hotorcool.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/hotorcool/
HBK	https://www.hbk-bs.de/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/hbk.braunschweig/ • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/hbkbs • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/hbk-braunschweig/ • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/hbkbraunschweig

VIC	https://valenciainnovationcapital.com/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/vlc-innovation/ • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@VLCInnovation • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/VLCinnovation • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/VLCinnovation • X: https://x.com/VLCInnovation
JIBE	https://www.jibe.company/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/jibe-company/ • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/JibeRomania
Città di Torino	https://www.torinoeuprojects.it/en/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/torinoeuprojects/ • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@torinoeuprojects
BFL	www.brugsfoodlab.be	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/brugsfoodlab • Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/@brugsfoodlab5116 • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/BrugsFoodLab • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/brugsfoodlab/
Rete CdQ	https://www.retecasesdelquartiere.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/retecasesdelquartiere/ • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/retecasesdelquartiere/
MoThess	www.thessaloniki.gr	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://gr.linkedin.com/in/resilient-thessaloniki-9a0a22337

- Facebook: <https://el-gr.facebook.com/cityofthessalonikiofficial>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/city.of.thessaloniki/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/cityofthessaloniki>

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